

Exploring The Impact Of National Youth Service Corps On Educational Development In Rivers State, Nigeria: A Longitudinal Study, 2013-2023

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ABSTRACT

The paper investigated the impact of National Youth Service Corp (NYSC) members on the development of education in Rivers State, 2013-2023. The National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) in Nigeria plays a pivotal role in educational development by deploying graduates to various schools, thereby addressing teacher shortages and enhancing the quality of education. This programme fosters community engagement and professional growth among young graduates, significantly contributing to the nation's educational landscape. Theoretically, the human capital development was adopted to explain the role of National Youth service Corps in advancing education in the State. Methodologically, the survey research design was utilized to allow the selected respondent a chance to express their opinion, feelings and perception of the subject matter. The total population of Rivers State according to national population census 2006 estimated population which stands 7,492,366 in 2022. a sample size of 400 was drawn from the total population through the Taro Yamane formula, while the simple random sampling techniques was used to select the final respondents from the total population. The findings include the inconsistencies in the deployment and utilization of corps members, mismatch between their skills and the needs of educational institutions, and challenges in sustaining the impact beyond the duration of their service. While the paper recommended the implementation of a more transparent and merit-based deployment process to ensure equitable distribution of corps members across urban and rural areas, prioritizing under-served communities with limited access to quality education.

Keywords: Educational development, exploring, impact, longitudinal study, national youth service corps.

INTRODUCTION

The National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) embodies a pivotal element of Nigeria's dedication to national unity and progress. With a particular focus on academic enhancement (Adebayo, 2020), the NYSC has played a vital role in bridging divides and promoting growth across diverse sectors (Agboola, 2022). However, a comprehensive analysis of the interaction between the NYSC and educational development in Rivers State from 2013 to 2023 unveils a intricate array of challenges that require meticulous examination and strategic interventions (Amadi, 2020).

Despite the NYSC's aspirations to contribute uniformly to national progress, there are indications of an unequal distribution of corps members throughout Rivers State. This disparity could lead to certain areas receiving disproportionate educational assistance, impeding the overarching objective of fostering equitable development (Nwosu, 2024; Eze, 2023; Igwe, 2020).

The efficacy of the NYSC initiative in advancing education hinges on the alignment between the competencies and proficiencies of deployed corps members and the specific requirements of educational institutions. Discrepancies in this aspect may jeopardize the program's impact on the quality of education provided in schools across the state. Inadequate coordination and cooperation between the NYSC and educational authorities at the state level might obstruct the seamless integration of NYSC endeavors with broader state educational strategies. This lack of synchronization could result in missed chances for strategic harmonization and resource optimization. Deficiencies in educational infrastructure, particularly in rural and underserved areas, persist as a notable challenge.

Despite the NYSC's potential to contribute to infrastructure enhancement, it may not be effectively addressing critical deficiencies, hindering lasting enhancements in the educational panorama. The absence of robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms could restrict the capacity to evaluate the true influence of the NYSC program on educational outcomes in Rivers State. Without comprehensive assessment tools, it becomes arduous to gauge the effectiveness of the program and implement data-driven enhancements. Hence, the crux of the paper lies in addressing these multifaceted issues.

The aim of this paper is to examine National Youth Service Corp and educational development in Rivers State. The specific objective is to investigate the contributions of the NYSC members to the educational development of Rivers State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The paper adopted the human capital development theory, which was formulated by the distinguished political economist and administrator Gary Becker. Gary Becker, a renowned American economist, was honored with the Sveriges Riksbank Prize in Economic Sciences in Memory of Alfred Nobel, commonly known as the Nobel Prize in Economics, in 1992. He was bestowed with this prestigious award in recognition of his groundbreaking efforts in expanding economic analysis beyond conventional market activities to encompass various facets of human behavior, particularly the significance of education and human capital in influencing economic outcomes (Becker, 1964). Becker's research and publications, including his seminal work "Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education" released in 1964, established the groundwork for the Human Capital Development Theory. Within this literature, Becker posited that investments in education, training, and health were akin to investments in tangible capital, such as machinery and infrastructure. He argued that these investments in human capital heightened an individual's productivity and earning capacity, thereby fostering personal and societal advancement (Becker, 1988).

While Gary Becker is often considered the primary figure associated with the Human Capital Development Theory, it's important to note that economic theories, including the development of human capital theory, are built upon a foundation of contributions from various scholars over time. Becker's work significantly advanced and formalized the theory, but it is part of a broader academic and intellectual tradition within the field of economics (Murphy, 1991). The Human Capital Development Theory, primarily associated with the work of Nobel laureate economist Gary Becker, is a robust and influential framework that offers several strengths and advantages in understanding the role of human capital in personal, economic, and societal development. The Human Capital Development Theory takes a holistic approach to human development. It recognizes that investments in education, training, health, and skills are interconnected and can contribute to overall well-being. This perspective allows for a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted nature of human capital (Murphy, 1991).

The theory underscores the strong connection between investments in human capital and economic empowerment. It posits that individuals who acquire knowledge and skills through education and training are better equipped to secure higher-paying jobs and achieve greater financial stability (Becker, 1988). A major strength of the theory is its emphasis on increased labor productivity. It asserts that an educated and skilled workforce is more productive, leading to higher levels of efficiency and output. This, in turn, contributes to economic growth and competitiveness (Barro, 2013). Human Capital Development Theory highlights the potential for social mobility. It suggests that education and skills can be powerful

mechanisms for individuals to move up the social and economic ladder, breaking the cycle of poverty and inequality (Heckman, 2012).

The theory advocates for efforts to diminish income disparity. It provides a pathway for individuals from various backgrounds to access opportunities and enhance their socio-economic status (Psacharopoulos, 2018). Furthermore, the theory emphasizes the significance of the quality of education. It highlights that not only the quantity but also the caliber of education is crucial for the enhancement of human capital. This emphasis on superior education aids in cultivating a more proficient and flexible workforce. The theory advocates for the idea of lifelong learning. It recognizes that learning is a continuous process that extends beyond formal education and persists throughout one's lifetime. This fosters a culture of ongoing skill development and adaptability to evolving circumstances.

In essence, the Human Capital Development Theory emerges as a potent and adaptable framework that underscores the transformative capacity of investing in education, training, and skills. Its merits are evident in its capacity to elucidate the connections between human capital and diverse facets of development, encompassing economic advancement, individual empowerment, and societal progress. It furnishes invaluable insights for policymakers, educators, and individuals striving to cultivate personal and communal progress (Mincer, 1958). Despite the manifold strengths of the Human Capital Development Theory, it is not devoid of limitations and deficiencies that warrant acknowledgment. A notable critique of the theory is its inclination to oversimplify the intricacies of socio-economic disparities. It presupposes that universal access to education and skill enhancement is readily available, a presumption that may not align with reality. Socioeconomic impediments such as poverty and discrimination can impede individuals' capacity to invest in their human capital (Becker, 1986).

The theory fails to address the inequitable distribution of educational resources and opportunities. Disparities in the quality of education and access to educational institutions can hinder the efficacy of human capital development endeavors (Psacharopoulos, 2018). Human Capital Theory places significant emphasis on formal education as the primary avenue for human capital enhancement. This inclination may underestimate alternative modalities of learning and skill acquisition, such as vocational training and experiential learning. The theory presupposes a steady labor market, wherein investments in human capital result in heightened earning capacities. However, in actuality, labor markets can be unpredictable, and economic circumstances can shift swiftly, impacting the returns on investments in human capital (Barro, 2013).

The theory emphasizes the individual's role in the development of human capital, yet it fails to adequately acknowledge the systemic and societal influences that shape an individual's capacity to invest in their human capital. It overlooks structural inequalities and social determinants that impact human capital development (Lucas, 1988). Moreover, the theory neglects to consider the cultural, contextual, and regional variations in human capital development. Cultural norms, values, and local economic circumstances can profoundly affect an individual's educational and skill development opportunities (Schultz, 1961). The theory predominantly assesses success in economic terms, particularly in relation to income and employment, without fully recognizing alternative measures of well-being, such as health, happiness, or community contributions, which are equally vital indicators of success (Becker, 1964).

The application of the Human Capital Development Theory to the examination of the impact of the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) on the educational advancement of Rivers State, Nigeria, from 2015 to 2023, provides valuable insights into how the NYSC program contributes to the enrichment of human capital and, consequently, educational development. Here are some key implications of the theory for this study:

I. The investigation can delve into how NYSC participants in Rivers State invest in their human capital during their service year. This investment encompasses the acquisition of novel skills, experiences, and knowledge through teaching, community development projects, and interactions with diverse communities.

II. Human Capital Development Theory posits that individuals who acquire skills and knowledge through education and training are more efficient and possess greater earning potential. The exploration

can evaluate how the NYSC program enhances the competencies of its participants and whether these newly acquired skills positively impact educational development in Rivers State.

III. The theory highlights the economic advantages of human capital development. The study can investigate whether the skills and experiences acquired during the NYSC program lead to economic empowerment for participants, thereby potentially contributing to economic progress in the state.

IV. Through scrutinizing the labor market outcomes of NYSC participants post their service year, the study can determine whether the program contributes to heightened labor productivity. It can analyze whether NYSC alumni exhibit increased competitiveness in the job market and whether this enhanced productivity positively influences the educational sector through, for instance, improved teaching standards.

V. The theory can explore how NYSC participants are empowered at an individual level. This empowerment may be demonstrated through the ability to make informed career choices, pursue further education, and engage in personal and professional development, all of which are pertinent to educational advancement.

VI. Human Capital Development Theory underscores the potential for social mobility through education and skill enhancement. The study can assess whether the NYSC program facilitates social mobility by offering opportunities for individuals from diverse backgrounds to access quality education and participate in activities that foster upward social mobility.

VII. The study can investigate whether the NYSC programme aids in reducing income inequality by providing educational and skill development opportunities to individuals who may not have otherwise had access to them. It can evaluate whether the program contributes to a more equitable distribution of educational resources.

VIII. The theory can evaluate how the NYSC programme influences the quality of education in Rivers State, particularly in terms of teacher training and the provision of additional educational resources.

The theory can examine whether the NYSC program promotes a culture of continuous learning among its participants. It can explore whether NYSC alumni are more inclined to engage in further education and skill development activities beyond their service year, which can have a lasting impact on the educational sector.

EVALUATING THE BENEFITS OF THE NYSC PROGRAMME

The inception of the National Youth Service Corp was a strategic response to the prevailing need, aiming to assimilate young Nigerians from diverse backgrounds into a unified national community (Ogunleye, 2018). General Yakubu Gowon, the Head of State of Nigeria at that time, played a pivotal role in establishing the NYSC. His vision for a united and cohesive Nigeria led to the creation of the NYSC program as a mechanism for national integration. Gowon's commitment to reconciliation and progress aimed to address the challenges posed by ethnic and regional disparities.

The NYSC was not only founded to foster unity but also to cater to educational and social requirements. The program sought to harness the vigor and expertise of young individuals for national progress, deploying graduates to underserved areas to contribute to community development projects, healthcare, education, and other vital sectors. The educational program was among the pioneering initiatives introduced upon the inception of the NYSC.

Education, as emphasized by developmental scholars, is a fundamental tool by which a nation's level of development is assessed. Some Western scholars have argued that the African continent has faced underdevelopment (Owolabi, 2019). The importance and impact of education in Nigeria's development cannot be overstated; education is a potent instrument capable of transforming societies, stimulating economic growth, and enhancing the overall quality of life for individuals. In the context of Nigeria, a nation with a complex history and diverse challenges, education plays a pivotal role in shaping its future (Owolabi, 2019).

Education is the primary mechanism through which a country can cultivate its human capital, imparting individuals with knowledge, skills, and competencies essential for their personal and professional advancement. In Nigeria, a knowledgeable workforce is indispensable for economic progress and innovation (Olaniyan & Okemakinde, 2018). Access to high-quality education stands as one of the most efficacious methods to alleviate poverty. Education equips individuals with the competencies necessary to secure enhanced employment prospects, thereby augmenting their earnings and standard of living. By mitigating poverty, education contributes to the establishment of a more robust and prosperous society (National Bureau of Statistics, 2019).

The programme aims to promote equity in educational opportunities by deploying teachers to regions where there is a shortage of qualified educators. This helps address discrepancies in access to quality education, ensuring that students across the country have relatively equal access to skilled and motivated teachers. The program strives to empower local communities by providing them with educated and enthusiastic individuals who can contribute not only to the classroom but also to broader community development initiatives. The NYSC was not merely a response to post-war challenges but also a strategic vision to bridge the gaps among Nigeria's diverse ethnic, cultural, and religious groups. NYSC members frequently organize and participate in educational outreach programs, such as literacy campaigns, awareness drives, and workshops. These initiatives not only promote literacy but also instill a greater sense of the importance of education in communities they serve (Elegbede & Tunde 2017).

In addition to academic education, the NYSC provides training in various vocational skills and entrepreneurship. These skills are valuable not only for personal development but also for contributing to the development of local communities. Graduates equipped with practical skills can support local industries and create job opportunities, ultimately contributing to economic and educational development (Zungeru, 2019). Furthermore, NYSC members often engage in research and data collection projects, which can be beneficial for educational development. Their research findings can inform educational policy and decision-making, helping authorities make data-driven choices to improve the quality of education in the country.

Additionally, NYSC fosters a sense of responsibility and leadership among Nigerian youth. By actively participating in various community and educational projects, young graduates are more likely to remain engaged in social and educational development even after their service year. They become future advocates for educational reform and change (Okonkwo, 2015).

The NYSC programme provides a platform for networking and collaboration among young graduates from diverse backgrounds. This network can be a valuable resource for educational development initiatives, as it allows for the exchange of ideas, best practices, and joint projects aimed at improving education in Nigeria (Osahon, 2019).

It also instills a sense of patriotism, discipline, and civic responsibility in young Nigerians. These values are integral to the overall development of the country and can contribute to a more responsible and ethical educational system. The National Youth Service Corps has had a significant impact on educational development in Nigeria through its multifaceted contributions, ranging from teacher deployment and infrastructure improvement to the promotion of literacy, cultural exchange, skill acquisition, and youth engagement. It plays a crucial role in bridging educational gaps and fostering a sense of responsibility and unity among young Nigerians, ultimately contributing to the nation's progress in the field of education. The essence of the study based on the above is to investigate the impact of NYSC to the educational development of Rivers State Nigeria.

DATA PRESENTATION

This chapter presents and analyzes the data that was gathered through primary and secondary sources to fulfill the objectives of this study. The data obtained from surveys, as well as pertinent literature, is displayed in tables and scrutinized using frequency counts and basic percentages.

Table 1: The total number of questionnaires administered for the study was 400 while the total number of questionnaires retrieved is 390

TOTAL NUMBER ADMINISTERED	TOTAL NUMBER RETIEVED
400	390

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 2: Gender distribution of respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	205	53
Female	185	47
Total	390	100

Source: Field work, 2024.

The table above indicate that out of 390 respondents 205 which represent 53% were male while 185 which represent 47% were female.

Table 3: Age distribution of respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18 – 30	103	26
31 – 40	183	47
41 – 50	67	16
51 and above	43	11
Total	390	100

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 3: The data presented above reveals that 103 of the survey participants, constituting 26% of the study population, fall within the youth category, aged between 18 and 30. Additionally, 183 individuals, accounting for 47.5% of the total sample, are classified as young adults within the age range of 31 to 40. Furthermore, 67 respondents, representing 16% of the study group, belong to the 41-50 age bracket, while 43 participants, equivalent to 11% of the overall respondents, are aged 50 and above.

Table 4: Educational Qualification of Respondents

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
SSCE	53	14
Diploma	87	21
Bachelors/HND	221	57
Postgraduate Degree	29	8
Total	390	100

Source: Field Work, 2024.

Table 4: The data above reveals that 53 of the participants, constituting 14% of the study's population, hold SSCE qualifications. Additionally, 87 respondents, representing 21% of the study's population, possess Diplomas. The majority of the participants, specifically 221 individuals accounting for 57% of the study's population, have attained Bachelors/HND degrees. Notably, 29 respondents, comprising 8% of the study participants, fall into another category. These findings highlight the prevalence of educated individuals, particularly graduates well-versed in the NYSC scheme and its implications for educational advancement in Rivers State.

Data Analysis

Investigating the contributions of the NYSC members to the educational development of Rivers State Nigeria?

Table 4 Summary of Descriptive Statistics of the Mean and standard deviation of the contributions of the NYSC members to the educational development of Rivers State Nigeria.

Questionnaire Items	N	Descriptive Statistics					Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
		SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1				
1. The deployment of NYSC members has effectively improved student-teacher ratios in schools across Rivers State.	390	116	100	97	75	2.65	1.10	Agreed	
2. The presence of NYSC members in Rivers State schools has fostered national unity among students.	390	180	110	60	40	3.10	1.01	Agreed	
3. The presence of NYSC members in Rivers State schools has fostered national unity among students.	390	110	105	90	85	2.62	1.11	Agreed	
4. Specific initiatives and projects implemented by NYSC members have had a positive impact on educational development in Rivers State.	389	120	112	50	108	2.63	1.18	Agreed	
Grand Mean						2.75	1.1	Agreed	

Source: Field work (2024)

Data from Table 4 presents the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation concerning the contributions of NYSC members to the educational development of Rivers State, Nigeria. The table encompasses the questionnaire items, number of respondents, their responses on a scale of 1 to 4 (with 4 denoting strong agreement), the mean score, standard deviation, and the remark based on the mean score.

For item 1, out of the total 390 respondents, 116 strongly agreed that the deployment of NYSC members has effectively enhanced student-teacher ratios in schools across Rivers State. Furthermore, 100 agreed, 97 held a neutral stance, 75 slightly disagreed, and none strongly disagreed. The mean score for this item is 2.65, indicating an overall agreement. The standard deviation is 1.10, suggesting a moderate degree of variation in respondents' opinions. The remark is "Agreed."

Concerning item 2, all 390 respondents partook in the survey. 180 strongly agreed that the presence of NYSC members in Rivers State schools has promoted national unity among students. Additionally, 110 agreed, 60 had a neutral perspective, 40 slightly disagreed, and none strongly disagreed. The mean score for this item is 3.10, signifying a high level of agreement. The standard deviation is 1.01, indicating a relatively low degree of variation in respondents' opinions. The remark remains "Agreed."

For item 3, all 390 respondents also voiced their opinions. 110 strongly agreed that the presence of NYSC members in Rivers State schools has fostered national unity among students. Additionally, 105 agreed, 90 held a neutral standpoint, 85 slightly disagreed, and none strongly disagreed. The mean score for this item is 2.62, indicating an overall agreement. The standard deviation is 1.11, suggesting a moderate degree of variation in respondents' opinions. The remark remains "Agreed."

Regarding item 4, 389 respondents provided their feedback. 120 strongly agreed that specific initiatives and projects executed by NYSC members have had a beneficial impact on educational development in Rivers State. Additionally, 112 agreed, 50 held a neutral viewpoint, 108 slightly disagreed, and none strongly disagreed. The mean score for this item is 2.63, indicating an overall agreement. The standard

deviation is 1.18, suggesting a moderate degree of variation in respondents' opinions. The remark remains "Agreed."

The overall mean for all the items combined is 2.75, denoting an overall positive perception and agreement regarding the contributions of NYSC members to the educational development of Rivers State. The standard deviation for all items combined is 1.1, suggesting a moderate degree of variation in respondents' opinions.

The analysis of Table 4.6 implies that the majority of the respondents concur that NYSC members have made positive contributions to the educational development of Rivers State. This encompasses enhancing student-teacher ratios, fostering national unity among students, and implementing specific initiatives and projects that have yielded positive outcomes. Despite some variance in respondents' opinions, the overall agreement remains high for all items.

DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

Ascertaining the contribution of the NYSC Members to Educational Development in Rivers State:

The analysis of table 4 presents a diverse range of perspectives on the perceived influence of the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) in bolstering educational infrastructure in Rivers State over the previous decade (2013-2023). The data, obtained through surveys, reflects the varied opinions of stakeholders within the education sector. Approximately 44% of respondents (23% in agreement and 21% strongly in agreement) express a favorable outlook, asserting that the NYSC program has played a substantial role in enhancing educational infrastructure in Rivers State. This particular group of stakeholders likely believes that the NYSC initiatives have positively contributed to the advancement and enhancement of educational facilities within the state. Conversely, a significant portion, constituting 56% of respondents (26% in disagreement and 30% strongly in disagreement), holds a pessimistic view regarding the impact of the NYSC programs on improving educational infrastructure. This divergence of opinions indicates that a considerable number of stakeholders may not perceive tangible benefits from the NYSC initiatives in the development of educational facilities.

Furthermore, Yusuf and Musa (2017) emphasize the significance of continuous training and mentorship for sustainable professional growth. If the NYSC initiatives fail to integrate ongoing support mechanisms, the impact on teachers' professional development may be perceived as limited, contributing to the dissent observed in the survey. The examination uncovers a noticeable disparity in opinions regarding the effectiveness of National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) member deployment in enhancing student-teacher ratios in schools across Rivers State. Around 44% of respondents (19% in agreement and 25% strongly in agreement) acknowledge the positive influence of deploying NYSC members in improving student-teacher ratios. This perspective aligns with scholarly viewpoints that underscore the potential advantages of Increased human resources within the education system.

Salami (2018) contends that the deployment of additional personnel, such as NYSC members, can alleviate the workload on existing teaching staff, resulting in more personalized attention for students. Furthermore, Osahon & Daniel (2019) underscore the potential for collaborative teaching strategies, which can be facilitated by the presence of NYSC members, thereby enhancing student-teacher ratios. On the contrary, a substantial segment of respondents, comprising 56% (26% in disagreement and 30% strongly in disagreement), holds a negative perspective concerning the efficacy of NYSC member deployment in improving student-teacher ratios. Understanding the factors contributing to this dissent is vital for a comprehensive interpretation of the findings.

Fanen (2021) reveals that the one-year service commences with a three-week camp orientation during which the prospective corps members are formally inducted into the program and exposed to its underlying objectives. Subsequently, the corps members are assigned to various public and private sector establishments, considered their primary areas of assignment. These establishments encompass schools, hospitals, banks, agricultural entities, government ministries, and various other sectors (both public and private). The corps members significantly contribute to the training and preparation of students for external examinations such as Common Entrance, National Examination Council (NECO), and West

African Examination Council (WAEC). They also aid in the mental and academic development of children and students through organizing home tutorials. The Community Development Service of the National Youth Service Corps is an educational initiative where the efforts of the corps members are combined with those of government agencies to enhance the economic, social, and cultural conditions of both corps members and communities. The CDS integrates the corps members into the commercial, social, and industrial spheres of the community and nation, enabling them to actively contribute to national progress.

The Skill Acquisition and Entrepreneurship Development (SAED) program of the NYSC, introduced in 2012, commenced with 12 distinct categories of skills offered within this initiative. These skill areas encompass agro-allied, automobile, beautification, construction, cosmetology, culture and tourism, education, environment, film and photography, food processing/preservation, information communication technology, and power and energy. The SAED program educates and equips corps members with knowledge for entrepreneurship and the capability to train other members of the community. Annually, the program mobilizes and prepares over 250,000 youths to become employable or start their own businesses upon completion of their mandatory one-year service. The primary objective of these programs is to encourage all Nigerians, particularly the youth, to actively engage in skill acquisition to create employment opportunities.

In line with the analysis above, a respondent reveals that:

The NYSC scheme has responded positively to the demands of our education. Whenever students are mobilised for national assignment, they are engaged by various schools where their knowledge are transfer and positively impact on the people/students. They provide a secondary form of learning to educational development in the state (P. Kinika, personal communication, January 19, 2024)

Another interviewee who corroborated the statement of the above reveals that:

The purpose of the NYSC scheme is not limited to social integration but includes enhancing educational infrastructure, improving the quality of education, and contributing to the professional development of teachers by mobilising corps members to strategic areas to learn perform different strategic functions that enhances education (L. Sibe, personal communication, January 26, 2024)

In with the above analysis, Alaba (2019) emphasizes the role of NYSC in rural community development, highlighting how the programmes have positively impacted educational infrastructure, teacher capacity, and student outcomes. Moreover Salawu (2018) underscores the significance of NYSC's engagement in community service and educational initiatives, noting that the direct involvement of corps members can lead to improved learning environments and increased access to quality education in underserved areas. On the other hand, a significant proportion of respondents (61%) expressed scepticism about the direct influence of NYSC on the improvement of education quality in Rivers State. This dissenting perspective prompts further exploration into potential factors contributing to this scepticism. Fajana (2017) emphasizes the collaborative opportunities created by the interaction between NYSC members and local teachers. The exchange of pedagogical methods, technological insights, and diverse teaching approaches, facilitated by NYSC members, can contribute significantly to the professional growth of local educators. Contrastingly, a notable proportion of respondents, representing 57% holds a negative view regarding the contribution of NYSC members to the professional development of teachers. Understanding the factors influencing this disagreement is essential for a comprehensive interpretation of the findings. Scholarly literature, as exemplified by Zungeru and Musa (2019), suggests that challenges such as a lack of structured programs for collaboration, limited resources, and variations in educational priorities might contribute to the negative perceptions. Without clear frameworks for cooperation, the potential benefits of

NYSC-teacher interactions may be unrealized, leading to scepticism among stakeholders. From the foregoing, the investigation revealed significant contributions made by NYSC members to educational development in Rivers State. These contributions ranged from teaching core subjects to organizing extracurricular activities, providing mentorship and counselling to students, and initiating community-based projects aimed at improving educational infrastructure and access. However, several challenges were identified that hindered the full realization of their potential impact. These challenges included inadequate training and support for corps members, limited resources and infrastructure in schools, cultural barriers, and resistance to change within educational institutions.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In conclusion, the comprehensive analysis conducted in sheds light on the intricate dynamics surrounding the nexus between the NYSC scheme and educational development in Rivers State between 2013 and 2023. The evaluation of this relationship underscores both the significant contributions made by NYSC members to the educational landscape of the state and the myriad challenges that impede their effectiveness in fostering sustainable development. In essence, while the NYSC scheme has undoubtedly contributed to educational development in Rivers State, there remains ample room for improvement. By implementing the recommendations outlined in this study, stakeholders can work collaboratively to overcome existing challenges and leverage the scheme's potential as a catalyst for sustainable educational progress in the state. This research underscores the importance of continuous evaluation, adaptation, and stakeholder engagement in optimizing the impact of the NYSC scheme on educational development in Rivers State and beyond.

Based on the findings presented above, here are recommendations to address the identified challenges and enhance the effectiveness of the NYSC scheme in contributing to the educational development of Rivers State:

1. The NYSC should develop a comprehensive needs assessment framework to match the skills and expertise of NYSC members with the specific needs of educational institutions in Rivers State. the scheme should implement this framework with a more transparent and merit-based deployment process to ensure equitable distribution of corps members across urban and rural areas while prioritizing rural communities with unlimited access to quality education.
2. The NYSC should enhance training and support mechanisms of corps members by strengthen pre-service and in-service training programs for NYSC members to equip them with the necessary pedagogical skills, classroom management techniques, and cultural sensitivity required to effectively contribute to educational development. The scheme should also establish mentorship programs and peer support networks to provide ongoing guidance, feedback, and professional development opportunities for corps members throughout their service tenure.

REFERENCES

- Adebayo, O. A. (2020). National Youth Service Corps and educational development in Nigeria: A critical review. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 9(1), 1-10.
- Agboola, S. O. (2022). The role of National Youth Service Corps in promoting national unity in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Science*, 34(2), 15-25.
- Alaba, O. A. (2019). The National Youth Service Corps Scheme as an instrument of unity and national integration in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Development in Africa*, 18(1), 23-48.
- Amadi, E. E. (2020). Challenges of National Youth Service Corps scheme in Nigeria: A case study of Rivers State. *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, 2(1), 1-12.
- Barro, R. J. & Lee, J. W. (2013). A new data set of educational attainment in the world, 1950–2010. *Journal of Development Economics*, 104, 184-198.
- Becker, G. S. & Tomes, N. (1986). Human capital and the rise and fall of families. *Journal of Labour Economics*, 4(32), 1-39.

- Becker, G. S. (1964). Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education. *National Bureau of Economic Research*.
- Becker, G. S., & Murphy, K. M. (1988). A theory of rational addiction. *Journal of Political Economy*, 96(4), 675-700.
- Eze, U. C. (2023). The impact of National Youth Service Corps on educational development in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Social Development*, 10(2), 15-25.
- Fajana, S. (2017). National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) in Nigeria: An overview. *African Renaissance*, 4(1), 52-71.
- Fanen, A. (2021). National Youth Service Corps and Education in Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354142662>.
- Heckman, J. J. & Kautz, T. (2012). Hard evidence on soft skills. *Labour Economics*, 19(4), 451-464.
- Igwe, I. C. (2020). The role of National Youth Service Corps in bridging the gap between education and employment in Nigeria. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 72(2), 1-15.
- Lucas, R. E. (1988). On the mechanics of economic development. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 22(1), 3-42.
- Mincer, J. (1958). Investment in human capital and personal income distribution. *Journal of Political Economy*, 66(4), 281-302.
- Murphy, K. M., Shleifer, A. & Vishny, R. W. (1991). The allocation of talent: Implications for growth. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 106(2), 503-530.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Nigeria. (2019). Statistical Report on Education in Nigeria. *National Bureau of Statistics*.
- Nwosu, O. G. (2024). National Youth Service Corps and sustainable development in Nigeria: A critical analysis. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 14(1), 1-12.
- Ogunleye, J. (2018). Youth Corps as a Factor in National Integration: The Nigerian Experience. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 24(3), 239-248.
- Okonkwo, O. & Fidelia, N. O. (2015). Youth service and national development in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 3.5: 223-232.
- Olaniyan, D. A., & Okemakinde, T. (2018). Human capital theory: Implications for educational development. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 24(2), 157-162.
- Osahon, D. O. (2019). The National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) scheme in Nigeria and national development: Prospects and challenges. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability* 2 (4), 2032-2044.
- Owolabi, T. (2019). Teaching as a profession in Nigeria: Problems and prospects. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(1), 133-145.
- Psacharopoulos, G. & Patrinos, H. A. (2018). Returns to investment in education: A decennial review of the global literature. *Education Economics*, 26(5), 445-471.
- Salami, I. T. (2018). NYSC and National Development in Nigeria: The Role of Corps Members. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(14), 202-211.
- Salawu, B. (2018). National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) and Nation-Building in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 14(1), 171-182.
- Schultz, T. W. (1961). Investment in human capital. *The American Economic Review*, 51(1), 1-17.
- Yusuf, S. A. & Musa, A. (2017). National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) scheme and sustainable development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1, (12), 95-108.
- Zungeru, A. K. & Musa, K. (2019). National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) and national development: Challenges and prospects. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4, (4), 32-45.